

Event metadata

Event title	Using Containers in Nextflow
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	17/06/2026
Time of event	1 - 2 pm AEST/ 12:30 - 1:30 pm ACST / 11 am - 12 pm AWST
Topic description	<p>Managing software dependencies is a common challenge when running bioinformatics workflows. Tools often require specific versions of libraries or conflicting environments, and analyses may need to run across different computational environments.</p> <p>Containers help address these challenges by packaging software and its dependencies into portable environments that can run consistently across computing platforms. Nextflow integrates container technologies directly into workflow execution, making it easier to run analyses without manually installing or managing complex software stacks.</p> <p>In this webinar, Dr Sarah Beecroft will explore how containers are used in practice within Nextflow workflows.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/containers-2026
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Workflows http://edamontology.org/topic_0769
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is designed for life scientists and researchers who are running Nextflow workflows and want to better understand how containers are used to

	manage software environments when executing pipelines.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	Participants will be able to understand how containers package software and dependencies into portable, consistent environments for bioinformatics workflows.
Speakers	Dr Sarah Beecroft, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre
Training materials	<p>Materials shared in this Zenodo record:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation slides (Containers_Nextflow.pdf) <p>Files and materials shared elsewhere:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recording of the presentation on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel: https://youtu.be/q4Rsq9QxEHk
Related material	None